

School-Life Balance: The Aftermath of Teenage Pregnancy Phenomenon

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Abstract:- This paper is a phenomenal study that used the descriptive phenomenological method developed by the American psychologist Amadeo Giorgi in the early 1970s to address the alarming rate of teenage pregnancies among nationalized high schools in the division of Surigao del Norte. Thus, the researcher opted to investigate this particular phenomenon. Whereas, as to the record of the Guidance Office of the concerned schools, there are about 17 young girls who have stopped schooling due to unplanned pregnancies and have returned to school after giving birth to their babies. Hence, the goal of this study is to explore and describe the lived experiences of pregnant teenagers about their pregnancy and how they balanced school-life roles. Guided by the grand tour question “How do you describe school-life balance as a teenage mom?” a scientific investigation was undertaken.

Keywords:- Teenage pregnancy; Teenage mom; Teenage girl; School-life-roles.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

With the rise in teenage pregnancy in this present culture, prevention became a large focus. Teenage pregnancy is defined as a teenage girl, usually between the ages of 13-19 becoming pregnant. The term in everyday speech usually refers to girls who have not reached legal adulthood, and who become pregnant. Per data gathered, teenage pregnancy in the Philippines rose 70% over 10 years and this number of teenage pregnancies in the country is an area of concern that the agency is giving serious attention, exposing as it does adolescent girls (10-19) to high risk (Ugochi, 2012). This is held locally in some nationalized high schools in the division of Surigao del Norte. As expected, this caused the dropouts of teenage girls who are pregnant. In particular, at Mainit National High School for five successive school years, an average of six students got pregnant which comprised around 1.5% of the female student population every year.

According to Makinano (2016) based on statistics there are 4 out of 20 females who got pregnant before the turn of 20 years old. She also stated in a letter that based on records Mainit had an increasing rate of teenage pregnancies and commonly indulged in this are teenagers as young as 12 years old. The consecutive occurrence of teenage pregnancy has been alarming thus the Provincial Health Officer-II (PHO-II) Dr. Ma. Isabel B. Makinano initiated the conduct of a symposium with a focus on Adolescent Reproductive Health and Common Complications during pregnancy last March 10, 2016, at Mainit National High School of which the audience is the female students of the school.

From a global perspective, the increase in several pregnancies among unmarried teenagers is recognized and now continues to be a global and local public health problem. As pointed out by Starks (2008), teenage mothers are even labeled as uneducated, financially unstable, and a burden on available government resources. This continues to be a problem for families, educators, healthcare professionals, and the government. It would not be safe to say that teenagers are not allowed to learn or receive reinforcement on God's laws on abstaining from premarital sex because religious education is not allowed in some public school systems. But, these teens are aggressive and lack control over their desires. Per a preliminary interview conducted, the common reasons for teenage pregnancy are curiosity, lack of sexual knowledge, financial and family problems, and uncontrolled emotions among teenagers.

These are young girls who have not yet finished schooling and do not have stable jobs to earn a living. It is imperative to note that a child having a baby as a teenager is more likely to face critical social issues like poverty, poor education, risky behaviors that lead to poor health issues, and child welfare. The financial cost of teens having babies is indeed financially devastating. According to Fair and Fearless Freeman (2005), there is a rising trend of pregnant young women in the country and most of them are unmarried. Young women are more vulnerable to death during pregnancy; hence they are not prepared physically and mentally for motherhood. This reflects that young women have adequate information about pregnancy.

The alarming rate of teenage pregnancies among nationalized high schools in the division of Surigao del Norte opted for the researcher to investigate this particular phenomenon. As to the record of the Guidance Office of the concerned schools, there are about 17 young girls who have stopped schooling due to unplanned pregnancies and have returned to school after giving birth to their babies. Hence, the goal of this study is to explore and describe the lived experiences of pregnant teenagers about their pregnancy and how they balanced school-life roles. Guided by the grand tour question “How do you describe school-life balance as a teenage mom?” a scientific investigation was undertaken.

B. Significance of the Study

All data obtained from this study would assist in the exploration of the experiences of pregnant teenagers in some nationalized high schools in the Surigao del Norte division. The findings from the study will be published and aimed at assisting policymakers in education and health during the policy formulation process concerning teenage pregnancy. The output of this research will be helpful to the school administrators as they will formulate, design and implement policies and programs on dealing with teenage pregnancy

cases in their schools. This would also help them in crafting ways to reduce the prevalence rate of teenage pregnancy and thus, reduce dropout rates as well.

This study will also provide guidance and assistance to some teachers and counselors to attain their goal of educating pregnant teenage girls in the school. This study is also significant to school counselors as this served as their frame of reference in planning, developing, and teaching healthy and appropriate relationships.

This study is also useful to parents who are searching for a consistent means of controlling their teenage children from engaging in premarital sex and thereby resulting in early pregnancy. This could serve as the basis for them to strengthen healthy communication and follow-up with their children, specifically the girls.

This study would significantly serve as an eye opener to teenagers and would somehow educate them about unplanned/unwanted pregnancies with the aim of preventing them. The findings of the study led to a better understanding of teenage students' beliefs about teenage pregnancy. Through this study, the female students could widen their view that becoming a teenage mom is not a hindrance to continuing their studies.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This study used the descriptive phenomenological method developed by the American psychologist Amadeo Giorgi in the early 1970s. This method is deemed appropriate to this study because it is aimed at describing a phenomenon from a psychological perspective. Relative to Giorgi's view, the researcher bracketed the assumptions pertaining to teenage mothers' phenomenon by refraining from positing a static sense of objective reality for oneself and the informants whose experiences are being studied. By this method, the researcher listened and attended to the descriptions of the informants without forcing the meaning of the descriptive units into predefined posting categories.

B. Sampling and Selection of Informants

The informants of this phenomenological study were acquired using the criterion-purposive sampling technique in order to ensure capturing the highest quality data. The informants assisted the researcher in constructing the reality they experienced. Their perceptions, beliefs, truths, and explanations provided the context necessary to arrive at the essence of the phenomenon. The participants offered information-rich "first-person accounts" of the experience essential to the study. Criterion sampling methods suited best because all the participants studied represented people who have experienced the same phenomenon (Creswell, 2007). The five participants who participated in the in-depth interviews were teenage mothers who by the time of the study are pursuing education.

Purposive sampling is defined as a type of non-probability sampling in which the participating units are selected on the basis of the researcher's judgment about which ones are the most useful or representative (Babbie, 2002) or according to the needs of the study (Glaser & Strauss; Morse, 1991). The selection criteria for inclusion were for teenage mothers who are currently attending school and caring or rearing their babies or school-going mothers who have returned to school after giving birth to their babies. This also included those who have stopped schooling and currently attending school and those who articulated their experiences related to the phenomena being investigated which is to provide details of school-life balance in the aftermath of teenage pregnancy. Prospective informants were referred which ensured that only women who met the criteria and wanted to tell their stories or wanted to be a part of this study were included. Thus, prior to the interview, the researcher asked the participants to sign a consent form.

C. Instrument

Sources of data in this study included unstructured or semi-structured interviews, observation, and documents. The choice of data sources is usually based on purposive sampling, which focused on collecting data from sources most likely to provide relevant information, as all of them had become pregnant as teenagers. A common aspect of most qualitative research data collection is participant's observation. In this situation the researchers observed and interviewed the participants. According to Creswell (2007), the subjects referred to as informants are usually chosen because they have experienced the phenomenon being studied.

D. Data Collection

In-depth interviews were used to collect and gather data. Hence, the data were collected during home visitation with each concerned informant. This is desired so as to protect the anonymity of the teenage mother or the participant. This also shunned the participants from spending money for transportation in going to the place where the interview was conducted. In every case, the researcher made every effort to make each participant feel relaxed and at ease. Prior to the interview, each informant signed an informed consent in the presence of their parents or guardian. This was important considering that the informants are minors.

The interviews were done in the presence of the parents of the participants. Interviews were conducted with informants using voice recording to enable transcription at a later time. A digital recording device was used. The researcher brought to the interview a list of semi-structured questions for the topics to be covered but was flexible with word choice and question order. In fact, the researcher translated the questions into vernacular, *Surigaonon*, or *Visayan* for clearer understanding on the part of the participants. While the tone of the interview was conversational and informal, the questions were comprehensive and semi-structured. The researcher used an adequate recording device when conducting interviews for later use when transcribing the interviews. The researcher

utilized an iPhone recorder, which is an application with the capability of recording voice. These recordings accompanied the field notes kept during the interview process.

E. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed according to a phenomenological psychological method developed by Giorgi (1985). The four essential steps of the Giorgi method, used in the analysis of this study's data, are described in the following stages:

➤ Stage 1. Reduction/Bracketing

An important and initial aspect of the data analysis is phenomenological reduction (or 'bracketing'). According to Husserl (1960) and Giorgi (1975), this is essential since it is only once this has been accomplished that more specific investigations can begin. Husserl (1960) used the word 'epoche' to describe phenomenological reduction, the aim being the 'suspension of belief' in the 'outer world' which prevents the researcher from making any judgments or having any preconceived ideas (Husserl 1960). The reality of the world is neither confirmed nor denied, it is 'bracketed' (Koch 1995). Paley (2007) commented that this suggestion is extremely radical because it involves the suspension of all judgments about the external world, not just the phenomena under investigation.

The researcher conducted each of the interviews personally, which helped enormously to 'get a sense of the whole.' However, the researcher also read each transcript several times to gain further familiarity with the words and the order in which they had been spoken. This was useful at a later stage when handling large amounts of data and associated paperwork. Care was taken throughout to ensure that it engaged with the words of the participants, with no attempt being made to interpret the meaning.

➤ Stage 2. Determine the transformed meaning units as expressed by the informant

This stage was achieved by reading and re-reading the transcripts until the meaning of the informant's message has been captured and then identifying areas of the interview that highlight the informants' experiences in relation to the phenomena under investigation (Whiting, 2001). These 'units' are separate entities, which together form the whole meaning of the experience. Giorgi (1975) stresses that when this phase of the analysis is undertaken; the attitude of the researcher must be one of 'maximum' openness', with the specific aim of the research not being taken into account at this point. Once the units have been isolated, the researcher must indicate, in a clear, simple manner, the theme which dominates each unit. Each of the transcripts will be read

carefully a number of times, highlighting the individual meaning units, as they appeared on the page.

Wertz (1983) has suggested that by doing this, the researcher is able to pay attention to what is being said and the manner in which it was iterated, 'empathetically dwelling' with the informants' experiences. As the researcher accomplished it, it was possible to re-read with the 'openness' that Giorgi (1975) describes and to identify a central theme for each unit. It is important to reiterate that the theme merely highlights the key issue of each unit as it appears to the naked eye, it does not attempt to relate it to the study or to interpret its meaning – this aspect is crucial to the use of Giorgi's method and cannot be over-emphasized.

➤ Stage 3. Transformation of the lived experience into psychological language

In this step, the delineated meaning units identified in the previous step were transformed into the "language of psychology that is currently tied to psychological perspectives (behaviorism, psychoanalysis, and so on)" (Giorgi, 1985, p.19). In the analysis, the researcher looked for 'perceptions' and 'emotions' that were expressed by the informants' descriptions in order to come up with the findings (Giorgi, 1985). It is at this point that the psychological intentions that are contained in the meaning of the description were developed. This step involved a transformation where the informant's first-person own everyday expression is changed into a psychological scientific language, which is in the third person. The idea was to interrogate the meaning units for what they revealed about the concept of learning.

➤ Stage 4. Formulating Description of Themes

As Giorgi's (1975) suggestion, this was conducted by formulating a description of each revelatory theme in relation to the specifics of the research situation. Giorgi (1975) acknowledges that these would certainly not be universal descriptions, but may be applicable to other situations. Giorgi (1975) suggests that this stage is particularly important since it allows 'feasible communication' to other sources. However, he stresses that this would not be the final word on the subject; the descriptions are intended to be considered further (Whiting, 2001). Having completed this aspect of the data analysis, the researcher has been able to consider, with relative ease, each revelatory theme which was generated, examining it in relation to relevant literature and illustrating it with participants' quotes. This stage formulated themes that concluded this research study regarding the school-life balance of teenage mothers.

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the Study

Figure 1 illustrates the flow of how the data were analyzed and interpreted in order to emerge the substantial themes of the study regarding the school-life balance of teenage mothers as the aftermath of teenage pregnancy which is the purpose of the study.

F. Ensuring Rigor and Trustworthiness of the Study

Burns and Grove (2003) proposed that five standards should be used to evaluate the rigor of qualitative research studies: (1) descriptive vividness, (2) methodological congruence, (3) analytical preciseness, (4) theoretical correctness, and (5) heuristic relevance. Descriptive vividness refers to the clarity and accuracy of the researcher's account of the study. This criterion was met for this study by the researcher's attention to the many details in the account of the study's procedures and a written presentation that brings the reader close to the data and its informants (Jose, 2008). The procedures were provided throughout data collection, data analysis, and findings attempted to keep the reader connected to the authenticity and originality of this study. Minute-to-minute proceedings specifically during interview sessions were recorded in the researcher's personal journal and digital recorder.

Methodological congruence, according to Burns and Grove (2003) is evaluated by how well the researcher meets (1) rigor in documentation, (2) procedural rigor, (3) ethical rigor, and (4) audit ability. To meet these criteria, the researcher accurately collected and recorded data through a digital recorder and used member checking directly with the participants to verify that the recorded data actually represented their stories. The participants were communicated with personally for further clarification in order to minimize possible errors in the interview and interpretation (Jose, 2008). Data analyzed to the point of emerging themes from the data gathered through interviews were presented to the participants for verification. No one identified misinterpretations or advised that changes needed to be made. The bracketing was determined sufficiently rigorous when member checks resulted in no requests for changes due to misrepresentation. Ethical rigor was

achieved by requiring written informed consent from each informant. The audit ability of this study was met at data coding and analysis was discussed. Raw data found in the digital recorder and transcripts of the narrative also constituted auditable records.

The last element of Burns and Grove's (2003) standards for establishing the rigor of qualitative studies is heuristic relevance. For a qualitative research study to meet this standard, the reader of the study's proceedings must have the capacity to recognize the phenomena described in the study, the theoretical significance of the findings, and the applicability of findings to teenage mothers.

In addition to evaluating the rigor of qualitative studies, trustworthiness or truth value is also an important determinant of the authenticity and usability of the findings. Basically, Lincoln and Guba (1985) established criteria for trustworthiness that are appropriate for all forms of qualitative research, including phenomenology. The goals of subjecting qualitative studies to examinations of their trustworthiness are related to determining whether or not the data reflect the truth of the phenomena of the lived experiences revealed by the study informants. The four criteria associated with evaluating the truth value of this study are credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. These criteria will be attained upon following the discussed proceedings of the study.

Credibility in qualitative research is concerned with confidence in the truth of the data and the interpretation of the data (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, the credibility of the study findings rests on the credentials presented by the participants that would prove that they are really teenage mothers. The credentials could be a birth certificate of the baby declaring therein the name of the informant as the mother. The interviews were recorded through a digital recorder and were backed up by the researcher's journal. The interviews were conducted in order to have reliable and authentic emerging themes upon doing the data analysis.

The researcher also applied member checking directly with the participants to avoid misinterpretations.

Dependability is the next criterion that was evaluated to establish the trustworthiness of a qualitative research study. Like the reliability-validity relationship in quantitative research, there can be no credibility in the absence of dependability. There are two suggested techniques associated with establishing dependability in qualitative research: (1) the stepwise replication, and (2) the inquiry audit. In order to establish stepwise replication, the qualitative study should involve several informants sharing the same qualifications for this study so that the results found by each can be compared and tested for reliability and validity. The inquiry audit involved the use of an external reviewer to scrutinize the data and all relevant supporting documents. In this study, dependability will be established through an inquiry audit.

Confirmability is associated with the objectivity and neutrality of the data in a study. In this study, confirmability was evaluated by the researcher's adviser and thesis writing committee when they determined the study's accuracy, relevance, and meaning. Confirming the closeness between the data and the emergent categories and themes contributed to positive conclusions that bracketing was successful (Ashworth, 1999). A detailed presentation of this study's methods, procedures, and findings of the auditable trial is required by the evaluators. Two independent auditors confirmed that the conclusions drawn by this investigator are true and rest on the thick and rich data provided in the interviews. Member checking, described earlier, was used to verify the researcher's findings and conclusions.

Transferability occurs when the findings from the data can be 'transferred' to other settings or groups and are similar to the concept of generalizability (Jose, 2008). The transferability of these study findings is yet to be determined. However, the researcher leaves a detailed and auditable trail that directs replication in other or similar populations.

G. Ethical Considerations

Ethical issues are equally significant in Giorgi's phenomenological study like any other research study. As a qualitative study, some ethical issues while performing this research were observed and practiced. The researcher religiously observed the following responsibilities to the participants such as should endeavor to ensure that participation in research should be voluntary; endeavor to ensure that decisions about participation in the research were made from an informed position, endeavor to ensure that all data were treated with appropriate confidentiality and anonymity, endeavor to ensure that research informants were protected from undue intrusion, distress, indignity, physical discomfort, personal embarrassment, or psychological or other harm.

The researcher applied the 'Moral magic' of consent in conducting the study. Giving consent confers rights on others and withholding or withdrawing consent withholds or removes those rights. Consent is a state of mind which is always referred to as an object – consenting to x, y, z and

'intentional state' (Hurd 1996: 125), therefore is changeable. Consent is not 'negligent ignorance', the likelihood of something happening just for knowledge of the occurrence of an action, just desiring an action. It involves a conscious choice to confer the right to do x y or z.

The researcher also followed the guidelines of professional expertise and standards and these are as follows; researcher endeavors to ensure that an appropriate research method was selected on the basis of informed professional expertise; endeavors to ensure that the researcher had the necessary professional expertise and support; endeavors to ensure that the research process did not involve any unwarranted material gain or loss for any informants; endeavors to ensure factual accuracy and avoid falsification, fabrication, suppression or misinterpretation of data; endeavors to reflect on the consequences of research engagement for all informants, and attempted to alleviate potential disadvantages to participation for any individual or category of person, endeavors to ensure that reporting and dissemination are carried out in a responsible manner (<http://www.respectproject.org/ethics/guidelines.php>).

Additional guidelines were properly observed also by the researcher to ensure the ethical considerations for the informants' benefits. The researcher endeavored to ensure that methodology and findings were open for discussion and peer review, and endeavored to ensure that any debts to previous research as a source of knowledge, data, concepts, and methodology should be fully acknowledged in all outputs.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Thumbnail Sketches

The one-on-one interviews took place within a one-month period. These interviews were face-to-face and consisted of 5 teenage mothers who by the time interviews were conducted were studying being already mothers. Talking with these women elicited many emotions and responses from the participants. Some became tearful as they remembered and recounted events in their lives. I allowed them to talk about their experiences without interjecting my own story. On the contrary, some were just happy to finally tell their own story. Interview questions were asked in English language but I deliberately injected translations of some words into the *Surigaonon* dialect for clearer understanding and smooth flow of the interviews.

B. Participant 1 (P₁)

Participant 1 continued schooling despite being pregnant. She did not stop and was so courageous to continue to report to her classes having a big tummy. There was no apprehension or feeling of fear in her as to what her teachers and classmates would say to her. What remained in her mind was to finish schooling having no idea whether her case would add insult to other teenage girls or may influence them. This relates to the "discourse of contamination" highlighted by Pillow as cited by Molapo (2011) which is more associated with the perception that the immorality of young mothers would teach other students bad behavior. Some of the teachers in high schools had the wrong

mentality that the young mothers' education was totally disrupted by their motherhood and would never recover. But the participant believes that continuing her studies is a good investment for her future and for her child's future, too.

Asked whether being pregnant affected her performance in school, she retorted "*medyo*" or just a little. It slightly disturbed her because she always felt sleepy inside the classroom revealing that "*Jaon magklase maam, tuyogon gajud ako. Matuyog ako sa klase*" or, every time she attended her class, she easily felt sleepy and eventually slept within the class. The participant also revealed that when she got pregnant it was nearly the end part of the school year. So, her grades were not that affected. "*Waya man sab ma'am. Kay Kuan naman adto ma'am fourth grading naman ma'am an exam*" narrated by the participant. Means, her grades were not affected because it was nearly the fourth grading period.

Oftentimes, teenage mothers are expressive and willing to return to school because of their future. This is evident in the response of Participant 1 saying for the "*future, Ma'am. Ako anak*" or, her coming back to school is for her future and that of her child. What would be her life like if she will not finish her schooling? This is her worry once she will stop from schooling. "*Sa ako sad kuan, kinabuh, kon dili ako moeskwela pa dajon, haman ako pasingud?*" explained by the participant. Marshall (2011) in her study revealed that pregnancy or parenthood is the key reason some left school. While teen pregnancy often causes students to drop out, being engaged in school can [reduce](#) instances of teen pregnancy. Teens who stay in school and are academically involved are less likely to get pregnant than their peers who aren't as engaged. In other words, dropping out also increases the chances that a teen will get pregnant.

She was slightly disturbed and felt hard balancing schooling and caring for her child as evident in her statement, "*medyo, Ma'am*". This means that she was slightly disturbed whenever her child got sick. She added: "*kay jaon hilabi jaon masakit maam, mahuna-hunaan nako sija, ing-ana...murag mabahin ako huna-huna*". She becomes anxious thinking about her child with bad health. That is why balancing her time between schooling and rearing her child seemed difficult. Marshall (2011) pointed out that the task of balancing their education and a baby proved impossible. However, things would be easy and manageable once there are support systems backing the teenage mother. Unlike others who have no one to depend on, Participant 1 is different because she has her aunt tending to her child if she is in school. Besides, her child's father supported her in rearing their child.

She has come to realize that it was very hard to balance schooling and caring for her child. Thus, she has this advice to teenage girls to really listen to their parents' advice and shun them from indulging in sexual activity which leads to getting pregnant.

C. Participant 2 (P₂)

On how to have a matured mind and how to overcome the big responsibility seemed disturbing Participant 2. She was worried on how to handle the situation being teenage mother or by that time, being pregnant and her schooling. Greathead *et al.* as cited by Molapo (2011) explained that teenage pregnancy often has numerous challenges in the life of young mothers and their children, such as poor performance and drop out from the system of education, unemployment and isolation from their age group. Such revelation is not far from the experience of Participant 2 as revealed in her statement "*mas greater na ang challenge ug mas bug-at ang responsibility na dapat nako i.i-balance dili ra kun ..uh..uh an ako responsibility is not focus only on myself but rather sa ... sa family then sa ... ako nasad bata*". In other words, being already pregnant has a bigger role and responsibility expected of her. The focus is not to herself but to her family, most especially to her child. When it is true that getting through school while pregnant is a challenge and the rewards are huge; but this is not so relevant to her because she was so disturbed and restless especially tending and rearing her child.

However, family support keep moving and kicking off pursuing to reach her goals of returning school and finish a course. She acknowledged the fact that she cannot stand alone without her parents. She averred that "*without the support of my family, I cannot stand alone. So, I will consider na mas greater an impact nan motivation nan parents sanan ila support sa imo. Morally, financially, tanan-tana nila na support, amo jaon kibali an naka motivate sa ako*".

It is obvious that teenage mothers who dropped out of school are products of the lack of support from school and at home. According to Tayler-Ritzler & Balcazar (2007), the support that they lacked at home included lack of child care assistance, like no family members, friends or boyfriends who were willing to provide child care. Teen mothers lacked encouragement which is related to school; maternal interference with their school enrolment and refusals to sign school enrolment forms. Meanwhile, Dench and Bellis (2007) disclosed that other barriers to further learning for teen mothers includes paying for and accessing childcare, and a need to keep teen mothers motivated and to address issues that arise once they enter mainstream learning.

However, she revealed that her child's father is supporting her "*in all...by all means, like financially, morally*". So, it was not difficult for her because she has all the support coming from her partner, parents and her child. She narrated that "*dili na karajaw kibali libog ako huna-huna kay ma focus naman ako kuan na sija jaon, an bata jaon then a family. So, kibali full force an kuan nila*" or her thinking was no longer hard and difficult because she has already a focus all because there is her partner, her child and her parents. The only time difficult for her to balance time between schooling and rearing her child when examination period is approaching and the baby is sick. It was so hard for her to focus studying and reviewing lessons for the exams as her time are often spent with her child. Participant 2 made it a point to maximize her time studying and tending

her child's needs. She wished to become an Accountant but then now changed to taking up Education course. Out from these experiences she came to learn to always do good and be good at all times. To all teenage girls, she has this advice to always do the right thing. She clarified in her statement that *"the right thing I mean is that you must not only be wise in choosing what to do. But at least, you know the consequence na imo gibuhat. At least, ready kaw sa bawat aksyon na imo tagbuhat. Dapat ready kaw kung unoy dapat mahitabo sa imo gibuhat. Awareness... mao to ako point"* meaning, one has to be wise enough in choosing what to do in life by knowing first the consequences of the action. One has to be ready to face the consequence of what was being done so as to ably manage them for a better outcome.

D. Participant 3 (P₃)

Definitely, the lifestyle of a teenage mother is affected being pregnant and having a child. In the statement of Participant 3, it can be gleaned that lifestyle has something to do with behaviors and attitudes. She said *"...jaon.kun buntis kaw di na gajud parehas sa una nan dayaga pakaw kay kun buntis kaw pirminti nakaw masuko tapos kailangan pakaw mag exercise... for sake sa baby tapos dapat mukaon kaw pirmi nang mga healthy...di na junkfood."* All she needs to say is that while being pregnant one has to control the emotion from always fuming towards persons, things and even situations.

One has to be conscious to go to exercise not for oneself but for the sake of the baby. One has to eat healthy foods and avoid junk foods. And for Baker (2014) life being pregnant at the early age has been difficult, but a blessing. Having a child forced one to grow up fast. One's childhood ended the day when a child is born and everything was no longer about oneself but towards the child. For Baker, who is a teenage mom, she said: *"After my daughter was born, I moved to Michigan to live with my mom and go to a new high school my junior year. I had to get used to leaving her all day, but I stayed on top of my work and maintained a 3.7 GPA until I graduated. I was more determined than ever to succeed academically because I knew it was an important step in making a better future—not just for me, but for us both."*

However, to Participant 3, life for a pregnant woman is really very hard. A lot of prohibitions and one should be careful what to eat. While in school, she has to adjust with the situation. Definitely, her studies were affected. She hardly behaves in the classroom. She easily gets sleep even during classes and cannot survive listening to her teacher discussing in the class. She said *"di nako ka-lungtad pagpamati kay sige ra maglingkod. Gusto ko anhi pirminti ra ako mag barat-barat, magbaktas-baktas."* Meaning, she wanted to stretch her body, to just do walking than sitting longer in the class. The Mayo Clinic (2016) averred that fatigue also ranks high among early symptoms of pregnancy. During early pregnancy, levels of the hormone progesterone soar which can make the mother or the pregnant woman feel sleepy.

Returning to school after delivery is always a right move for teenage mothers. For Participant 3, she returned school for economic purpose. She wanted to be economically stable in the future and achieving this dream is through finishing her studies. Besides, she said *"nubalik gajud ako pag skuyla kay para di sab ko dali ba kanang dali tamayon ng tawo. At least kung kuan man ko na... unu pa ini, bahala nabuntis man ko ng sajo at least makita ng tawo na kuan gihapon ko kanang naa koy maipakita sa ila. Na in short, nasapdok man, mobangon gajud."* In other words, she returned school to finish a course so that people would not undermine her. Rejection by people surrounding can be very difficult to bear by a teenage mom. She relented that though she got pregnant and have a baby now, she has something to be proud of and that is her career or education. Salazar (2015) recounted that teen pregnancy alters the life of a young woman and negatively impacts her ability to attain educational goals. Yet, this is contrasted by Participant 3 by emphasizing that she tried hard just to finish schooling and eventually find a stable job for her and for her child's future.

However, she disclosed to have met difficulty balancing her time reporting to class and rearing her child. It was hard for her breastfeeding her child and so this made her carefully balanced her time. This relates to Samuel as cited by Molapo (2011) stating that teenage pregnancy and mothering often bring a halt to the teenager's education. Teenagers who leave school to deliver their babies always have to struggle to catch up in their classes. They have to split their time between their classes and their babies. They may try very hard not to fall behind in their class work, but they always miss some examinations, which is very hard to recover from.

But these realities never thwarted or hampered Participant 3 to pursue her goals. Nevertheless, teenage mothers should not be discouraged to return to school amidst many troubles and challenges. Willan (2014) once said that teen moms should not be stigmatized; they should be encouraged to finish school. The government and society as well as the families or parents have a legal and moral obligation to support her to remain in school and return after she gives birth. Schooling is her right and will determine her and her child's future. Supporting teenage mothers to complete their education is the most powerful intervention the society can make for both the teenage girl and her child.

And so, Participant 3 revealed that her parents are all supportive of her. In her statement *"kay kun labi na kun jaon waya ako, jaon klase nako. Tapos wayay makabantay jaon gajud sila magbantay ng bata."* It says, when she is out for school, her parents find time to take good care of her child. Financially her parents are backing her up. She said: *"Aw financially sab labi na kay teenager pa ako waya pakoy kuan gajud na may masuporta sa bata. Jaon sila mama sanan si papa mu kuan, mupalit ng kinahanglanon."* Just because she was then still studying and having no enough income to support or sustain her child, her mother and father are the ones who bought things needed for her baby. So, for all these facts, she has this to advice teenage girls: never ever dare to enter relationship and dating. This is the start of

getting entangled to unplanned pregnancies. Life being one is not easy but always hard. This could really destroy the future of the teenage mom and the child as well. She ended by saying, think first before doing something and try to imagine ahead the outcome of your actions. “*School first gajud anay for now*” or, make sure to prioritize schooling for now.

E. Participant 4 (P₄)

She got pregnant when she was in third year high school. Since then, she became helpless and cannot think wise being pregnant at a younger age. She felt embarrassed to her teacher and classmates. She cannot afford to think being the cause of talks, backbites and issues. She simply appeared uneasy all the time in the school. She seemed to have experienced undue pressure from teachers, peers/ classmates and the community they live in. It is true that some young mothers are, thus, marginalized and excluded from peers. For this reason, some girls decide to leave school.

But, Participant 4 is an exception. She returned school even if it was hard for her to balance her time. It really affected her studies because she hardly can focus in the class. Now that she has a child, she cannot help but to think always of her child back home especially if the child is sick. However, she was able to survive all because she was then determined to finish schooling to be proud of before her child. She was motivated to continue because “*sa ako na hunahuna na gusto nako mueskwela na jaon mahuman ako na an ako future, na mueskwela para sa ako bata na masundog sad ako nija na ako mamanakatapos nan fourth year. Ako sad mutapos sad ako nan fourth year.*” In other words, she thought of finishing up to fourth year high school for her child to emulate him. The condition really affected her of balancing her time for school and for her child. The worst thing is when and during the time when the baby is sick.

As a matter of fact, Freeman & Rickels, as cited by Salazar (2015) that teenage childbearing is surrounded by consequences that disrupt their education since teenage mothers are more likely to have dropped out of school than their non-pregnant peers. Hence, Grant and Hallman (2006) attest to this by showing that in most cases, the birth of a baby signals the end of schooling for the teenage mothers. It is very difficult for teenage mothers to complete or succeed with their schooling.

Hence, Participant 4 came to realize that life would be different to come to school already married; having a husband and a child is exactly difficult and different. Every time the baby cries unceasingly, only a mother can pacify and can make the child come down and cry no more. So, one has to leave school and attend to the needs of the baby. Having this kind of phenomenon, she gives such advice towards teenage girls to stop from following her direction.

Instead one has to focus to her studies; listen to the teachers; should not go out for dating and others that could mar her dignity.

F. Participant 5 (P₅)

Her pregnancy made her fearful from her parents' wrath upon knowing her condition. She kept this secret and yet, she found time to reveal it to her parents. She has some symptoms of being pregnant like constant coughing and feeling asleep all the time. Since then, she came to school always late because of waking up late for sleeping too long. Her study habit was affected at the very least level.

But despite all these, she continued to come to school and finish a course. After all, it would be hard to apply or look for job being not a full-fledged graduate. She said in her statement that she was particularly motivated to return to school for the future, “*para sa future sa ako bata. Ako sab gihuna-hunaa nga, kung di nako ipadayon, di man sab kung... manarbaho na ko dili dayon dali madawat ing-ana gani.*”

Thus, she endured the consequences even it was hard for her to balance school life and rearing her child. It was hard because “*kung mag study ka sa gabie, kinahanglan magpatulog pa kag bata ing-ana. Unahon man jud nimu pagpatulog kay kung mag study ka tapos dili pa siya tulog, musamok man gyud. Samuk-samukon man ka*” in other words, a child always misbehaves at night and demands the mother's attention or tender loving care. Therefore, the mother should prioritize her child over her studies. One could be disturbing by the child if the latter is not yet asleep.

After the analysis of the five interviews, three core themes emerged. The first, has something to do with how the teenage mothers deal with challenges that place extra demands not only on their stage of adolescent development but also on their ability to adapt to their new role as a parent. Three participants spoke about needing to adjust to the pregnancy. This has something to do with the teenage mothers' relationship with significant others, especially their parents and friends.

One of the participant shared that she has hard time revealing or telling her parents about her condition. At the start, she was so apprehensive and reluctant of telling it to her parents. She was afraid, but she needed to tell her parents. After all, she would need them. Then, she was able to tell them only after three months being pregnant. “*Sugod, siyempre hadlok man gyud na nga ingnon sa ginikan..kay amo man lage binohatan na kuan...pero kinahanglan man gyud ingnon kay ginikanan mangyud ka mo..kibali mudepende man gyud ka sa imong ginikanan. Mao to pag-giingnan gyud nako sa ako ginikanan pero kibali kuan na ..tulo na ka bulan.*”

Table 1: Sample Transcripts of the Informants with its Psychological Meaning Unit, Conceptual Category and Themes

Lines	Natural Unit	Transformed Meaning Unit	Psychological Meaning Unit	Conceptual Category	Theme
P ₅	<i>Sugod, siyempre hadlok man gyud na nga ingnon sa ginikan..kay amo man lage binohatan na kuan...pero kinahanglan man gyud ingnon kay ginikanan mangyud ka mo..kibali mudepende man gyud ka sa imong ginikanan. Mao to pag-giingnan gyud nako sa ako ginikanan pero kibali kuan na ..tulo n aka bulan.</i>	Finding it hard to reveal to parents the condition of early pregnancy	Felt difficulty to tell the truth to the parents	Fearful status being pregnant at a teenage stage	Adjustment to the Pregnancy
P ₅	<i>Kuan...sa ako...sige ko obhon..ubo-ubo ubo gyud. Kibali aikong kuan kanang gidala man kunu tawag...</i>	Coughing regularly as brought by being pregnant	Being susceptible to all germs when pregnant	Immune system is lowered during pregnancy	Adjustment to the Pregnancy
P ₁	<i>Kuan...maglipong-lipong ako maam tapos jaon mga baho na mga baho gajud sa ako hilabi na jaon ajos ako gayud isuka, musuka gajud ako jaon.</i>	Feeling dizzy due to odors during pregnancy	Heightened sense of smell during pregnancy	<i>Perception towards odors changes during pregnancy</i>	Adjustment to the Pregnancy
P ₁	<i>Kuan, maintain ako tuyogon...ing ana gajud ako. Tuyogon tapos maglipong-lipong ako.</i>	Getting always sleepy and dizzy oftentimes	Dizziness and sleepiness as pregnancy side-effects	Dizziness and fainting common during pregnancy	Adjustment to the Pregnancy
P ₃	<i>Kuan...jaon..kun buntis kaw di na gajud parehas sa una nan dayaga pakaw kay kun buntis kaw pirminti nakaw masuko tapos kailangan pakaw mag exercise...</i>	Getting irritable while being pregnant	Irritability of pregnant women is caused by changes in progesterone	Irritability as one of the emotional challenges of being pregnant	Adjustment to the Pregnancy

Three of the participants have shared that being pregnant has brought them changes of their behaviors and attitudes as part of the adjustment they experienced during pregnancy. According to Kimmel as cited by Nierenberg (2016) pregnancy is a huge transition in a woman's life, and it involves a complex mix of emotions, both good and bad. It can also be said that these behaviors and attitudes of the pregnant women can affect her relationship with her friends, parents and even classmates in school. Though, plenty of attention is given to the physical changes and discomforts in a woman's body during pregnancy, but the emotional changes she could be experiencing may not always get discussed. So, while in school and being pregnant, one has to bear being irritable and moody. During the nine months, a woman's moods and emotions can range from the highs of feeling overjoyed and excited about having a baby to the lows of feeling impatient, worried and terrified as the delivery and motherhood approaches.

The second, the theme that calls for adjustment and balancing one's time for schooling and parenting. The participants described the pregnancy as influencing their motivation to do well in school and to be successful both as student and as a mother to their child. There is also this impression or speculation that their lives were or might be difficult in the future, but they were determined to proceed and live a successful life and provide for their baby. Taukeni (2014) in his study revealed that being a student mother is difficult to find enough time to navigate between studying and parenting. He asserted that significant difficulty for mothers who are students is lack of time to spend with their children, partners, extended families and friends, and to study and complete assignments.

Hence, Mitchell (2008) argues that unfortunately, as dedicated as single mothers are to both their children and their education, in the end, the time crunch can have devastating effects on the relationship with their children. One participant said: “...mas greater na ang challenge ug mas bug-at ang responsibility na dapat nako i-balance dili ra kun..uh..uh an ako responsibility is not focus only on myself but rather sa ... sa family then sa ... ako nasad bata.”

In other words, there is a greater challenge of being pregnant at teenage stage. One needs to be responsible in balancing time and focus. It was when before she has to focus on herself, this time she has to focus on her family especially to her child. It is really not easy to assume the role of being teenage mom while at the same time returning to school. One needs to have focus. Not only to her studies but more so with her child. There are others who do not have much time with their child as lots of their times are apportioned to their studies. One study revealed: “*It is not easy, sometimes when I want to plan during my SBS (School-Based Studies) the baby is crying or I need to change the nappy. I do not have much time to do my role as a mother because I leave for home late around 4:00 PM where I find the nanny already wash him and change him. I only used to be with him during the weekend. It is not easy to be a student mother; you start to lose some friends but you just need to focus on your study. It is not that you lose them but they will not want to walk with you. When you walk alone and people are looking*

The same goes with the participant of the study upon revealing that: “*Mabahin ako huna-huna sa pagtuon, sa pag skwela sanan jaon pag kuan sad sa bata kon unoy ako kuanon mabahin ako huna-huna ba na na nasakit an bata, tapos skwela, jaon matunga imu huna-huna gani na kon kintahay masakit an bata, skwela ako, adto ra ako huna-huna sa bata kon na uno na ako bata na nasakit.*”

Her time is really divided between her studies and parenting her child. There are times she came to think what if her child gets sick. She always thinks of the future and the condition of her child. Molapo (2012) once said that teenage pregnancy and mothering often bring a halt to the teenager's education. They have to split their time between

their classes and their babies. There would be times and circumstances that they would miss their classes and even examinations. This really calls for an increased motivation and proper balancing of their time for schooling and parenting.

The Merriam-Webster (2014) defines motivation as the act or process of giving someone reason for doing something: a force or influence that causes someone to do something. For these five (5) women participants, motivation came in many ways. For some it was the feeling of needing to prove others wrong. One participant once shared: “*Then nubalik gajud ako pag skuyla kay para di sab ko dali ba kanang dali tamayon ng tawo. At least kung kuan man ko na... unu pa ini, bahala nabuntis man ko ng sajo at least makita ng tawo na kuan gihapon ko kanang naa koy maipakita sa ila. Na in short, nasapdok man, mobangon gajud.*”

She returned school to prove to others that she has achieved one important goal and that is of finishing a course or getting proper education. Despite getting pregnant at the early stage, she has something to be proud of before others. Sibanda and Mudhovozi (2012) pointed out that completing high school and managing with school work both at school and at home is a tough mission foremost of the teenage mothers. Finishing school and participating in activities after the child is born becomes a big chore. One participant shares that: “*...it gets difficult for me when I am at home because in order for me to do my homework or study I have to wait for the child to sleep. It is then that I can focus on my studies. Sometimes the baby doesn't sleep until late by the time she sleeps, I am also tired and sleepy and cannot do my school work.*”

Likewise, the ability to show their worth was a motivating factor for some of the participants interviewed. In general, as teen mothers, some women were often times looked down upon and dismissed by society. Some were told by those they thought they could trust that their lives were over or they might as well give up since they were pregnant. For these women, that was not an acceptable frame of mind. They knew their own potential and set out to show others what they were capable of achieving.

Table 2: Sample Transcripts of the Informants with its Psychological Meaning Unit, Conceptual Category and Themes

Lines	Natural Unit	Transformed Meaning Unit	Psychological Meaning Unit	Conceptual Category	Theme
P ₁	<i>Sa ako sad kuan, kinabuhi, kon dili ako moeskwela pa dajon, haman ako pasingud?</i>	Where to go when not able to finish school?	Being uneducated loss self-image and direction	Unschooling or illiteracy makes one troubled	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₂	<i>...exam is approaching then here comes the baby nagkasakit or kun dili man nagkasakit, kinahanglan na jaon kaw or kanang aside na magtuon kaw di kaw katuon kay divided naman ang time kay jari pa may bata atimanon. Unahon an bata, I platar asa ang bata adisir kibalang study...</i>	Examination period is approaching and the baby gets sick...balancing time is difficult but one has to focus to the child	The need to have a balance between emotional and mental needs both of mother and of the child	Balancing emotional and mental stresses	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₃	<i>Then nubalik gajud ako pag skuyla kay para di sab ko dali ba kanang dali tamayon ng tawo. At least kung kuan man ko na... unu pa ini, bahala nabuntis man ko ng sajo at least makita ng tawo na kuan gihapon ko kanang naa koy maipakita sa ila.</i>	Returning to school to have something to prove amidst failure by getting pregnant early	The need to finish studies despite having pregnant and as teenage mom	Balancing schooling and parenting	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₃	<i>Kay jaon..uhmm oh maglisud gajud ko kay kun mu skuyla ako ng buntag simpre breast feed. Kun magpa breast gajud kaw pak. Tas pado-do. Pagkahuman mukari kaw sa skuylahan kay 7:30. Tapos gajud amo jaon taglaung balance na gajud kaw nan imo time</i>	Difficulty adjusting time breastfeeding and of coming to school	The need to breastfeed and reporting to school	Balancing schooling and parenting	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student

Table 2 continued. . .

Lines	Natural Unit	Transformed Meaning Unit	Psychological Meaning Unit	Conceptual Category	Theme
P ₄	<i>Sa ako na huna-huna na gusto nako mueskwela na jaon mahuman ako na an ako future, na mueskwela para sa ako bata na masundog sad ako nija na ako mamanakatapos nan fourth year ako sad mutapos sad ako nan fourth year</i>	Likes to finish school for her and her child's future; to being her child's model of finishing even up to fourth year high school	The need to achieve educational status in life	Studying to earn a course and to be looked up to by children	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₄	<i>...Tapos mabahin imo pag skuyla..tapos maka absent kaw kay nahilantan an bata tapos jaon mulaong na magpabakuna di' maka absent kaw kay isa man kaw ka ginikanan ikaw gajud an kuanon sa bata labi na pagmagmanya, nanay gajud an hanapon.</i>	Being caught between studying and attending sick child and incurring absences from classes	The need to being present both in school's activities and child's need for time and affection	Parental presence is always at stake towards child's need	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₄	<i>Pagka buntag maghanap sad nan Mama...di' ako nasab ..di' madugay pag eskuyla</i>	Every morning, the child always looks for the mom....so comes to school late	The need of mother's touch, tender and loving care	Mother's time and presence is always necessary	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₅	Para sa future sa ako bata. Ako sab gihuna-hunaa nga, kung di nako ipadayon, di man sab kung... manarbaho na ko dili dayon dali madawat ing-ana gani	For the child's future. Thinking clearly that not finishing school makes one hardly employed	The need of proper education to land a better job	Getting educated assures one of a better job	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₅	<i>Yes, difficult jud. Kibali, siyempre..kung mag study ka sa gabie, kinahanglan magpatulog pa kag bata ing-ana. Unahon man jud nimu pagpatulog kay kung mag study ka tapos dili pa siya tulog, musamok man gyud. Samuk-samukon man ka</i>	Difficulty balancing time to study and getting the baby sleep in order not to disturb in studying	The need to balance time between studying and caring/rearing the child	Balancing schooling and parenting	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student
P ₁	<i>Kuan..an ako ika share sa ila na lisod man na mag eskwela kaw tapos jaon pay bata ariglaron grabe gajud kalisod hilabi na pagmasakit...</i>	It's hard to go on schooling while attending a child especially if he gets sick	The need to focus both for schooling and of caring the child	Difficulty to becoming responsible to school and parenting	Increased motivation to do well as mother and as a student

Eventually, above mentioned themes of teenage mothers their difficulties and challenges within their perspective has been fully described, in three narrated eminent themes and expound. Yet, the author does not give any specific word that contemplate the specific title of each

theme, it is up to the readers on how he/she emphasize those themes. Below in figure 2, is an imaginary paradigm that showcase on how teenage mom balance their life during pregnancy and after pregnancy.

Fig. 2: Eidetic Framework of the School-life Balance among Teenage Moms as an Aftermath of Teenage Pregnancy

The figure shows the eidetic framework of the school-life balance as experienced by the teenage mothers. It shows the relationship of the surrounding themes to the central idea and how the information in the outer ring contributes to the central idea. The three surrounding emergent themes such as _____, _____ and _____ are the Ways to Ensure..... _____ which is the dominant theme at the center. It can also be said that these three emergent themes are best anchored with the Hierarchy of Needs Theory of Maslow and Herzbergs' Theory of Motivation which clearly emphasized the use of motivation to be able to meet a particular need. Motivation here refers to teenage mothers' ability to balance their lives between schooling and parenting coming from the situation of being teenage mother. In other words, the concentration of such theory is on needs of the teenage mothers to be able to balance life. While Vroom's theory holds a fact that people have different set of goals and out of these goals derived motivation to do well both in schooling and parenting as these are being expected of them. When Hierarchy Theory of Needs and Motivation speak of being motivated to reach and achieve the needs, the expectancy theory focuses on outcomes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the research concludes that teenage mothers face many challenges along the way which have potential to affect and disturb, disrupt and interrupt their decision to return school and while already in school and of achieving academic success and performance. It can be concluded that having two roles as mothers and students is but a confusing and hectic jobs. Hence, the main common challenge teenage or student mothers experience is lack of time to manage their dual roles. In other words, they have found it very difficult having school-life balance.

It can be concluded that other challenges emerged and are emerging to include lack of time to both schooling and parenting, being drowsy, weak and lonely. Even though family and friends provide support some of them still cannot attend classes due to worries of leaving their children at a bad or poor health condition. The greatest fear seen among the participants is of having occurrence and possibilities of their children to get sick.

While the themes identified through this research are insightful and interesting, it should be remembered that the goal of this research was to examine what this experiences like for adolescent females. The goal of collecting qualitative data is to gain an in-depth understanding of an experience. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that these findings cannot be generalized to a wide range of adolescents or teenage mothers. Hence, they merely represent the descriptions provided by this group of participants and serves as a beginning to understanding issues related to the teenage pregnancy.

V. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study exposed the fact that these teenage mothers are incredibly strong and resilient. Their decision to return to school can be a good example of being conscious about achieving goals in educational pursuits. As there are lots of people who may not aware of other women who have been in similar situations, yet were able to reach their dreams and fulfill their potential. This study and its findings serve as an awakening among teenage mothers who desired to live in oblivion to change, renew and think positive that there is hope. In fact, these young women deserve to be seen as role models because they stand up and face the challenges than remain unchanged or obscure with their conditions.

The result implies that family, school and community supports are needed for these teenage mothers to really recover from the downfall. This exposed a great need and opportunity for these groups to step up and provide a central role in changing the path of girls who find themselves pregnant. This will in no way encourage others to become teen mothers themselves; instead it will provide an alternate reality for teen mothers. In a typical Filipino family, it is a reality that families most likely consist of a mother and father who are mutually engaged in the rearing and nurturing of their children.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the given summary of findings, conclusions and implications, the following are recommended:

- School authorities should address and include as part of the school curriculum future teen mothers' problems and special needs;
- All schools must have a policy on teenage pregnancy and mothering where all problems and challenges of these young mothers can be discussed and addressed;
- There should be a guidance and counseling office in every school to help young people with sexuality issues and career guidance, and many others;
- A need to conduct studies to investigate the impact of teenage pregnancy and mothering on educators and other learners in schools.

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